

Project information

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Document information

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V0.2	21-05-2021	Elke Plönjes, Ute Krell	Amendments

LEAPS-INNOV Kick-off Video Meeting: ScreenShot Photo

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LEAPS-INNOV kick-off Meeting Description

The LEAPS-INNOV kick-off meeting took place on 20 and 21 April 2021 with over 140 participants, in a digital format (Zoom meeting) due to the pandemic situation.

The Plenary session on Day 1 started with a cordial welcome from Helmut Dosch, DESY director and co-initiator of the LEAPS consortium, expressing his pleasure to see this major pilot starting. LEAPS-INNOV will implement first steps of the LEAPS technology roadmap while at the same time, it initiates a long-term partnership with industry, especially SMEs. Patricia Postigo McLaughlin, who was the European Commission’s project officer during the application and grant agreement phase of LEAPS-INNOV, added an introductory statement on the new framework program Horizon Europe.

Elke Plönjes, scientific coordinator of LEAPS-INNOV presented an overview on the project, how LEAPS-INNOV will contribute to solving key technological challenges for the next generation of photon sources, the upcoming diffraction-limited storage rings and the still novel X-ray FELs. She shortly presented the technical work packages encompassing advanced accelerator technology, improving the European capabilities for production of high-performance X-ray mirrors and diffraction gratings as well as efficient sample delivery systems with higher spatial and time

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resolution. Additionally, higher-performance detectors are essential for efficient use of these light sources, and the enormous amounts of data they produce require a structured Europe-wide effort to manage data reduction and compression. The work packages are supported by an overarching industry networking and relations work package and complemented by pilot activities together with user consortia. The equal opportunity officer Deike Pahl (European XFEL), who was officially approved by the LEAPS-INNOV governing board during the second day, and the data protection officer Carsten Porthun (DESY) were introduced to the participants.

Ilka Mahns (DESY ITT) presented information on intellectual property rights, as requested by WP leaders. She reminded all that the main aim is to create added value for involved parties through cooperation and bring new technology from research to market. A training on IP will be organized as part of WP8 (industry relations).

The Work packages spent the rest of the day in individual and combined meetings to further kick-start the project tasks. The outcome of these meetings was presented to all project members on Day2. Thereafter, Ute Krell presented how the LEAPS-INNOV governance has been set up and how the project LEAPS-INNOV and the LEAPS consortium will be linked as well as how the Innovation Advisory Board and the RI Co-innovation platform (jointly with other RI innovation projects) are planned to be set up. Finally, Elke Plönjes wrapped up the meeting and thanked for participation.

The agenda and the general presentations are uploaded on the INDICO event page.

LEAPS-INNOV kick-off Meeting Agenda

20 – 21 April 2021

Agenda

About: In the context of open innovation, the LEAPS-INNOV pilot project focusses on the implementation of new strategies and activities for long-term partnerships between industry and the European light sources, synchrotrons and free-electron lasers, with their tens of thousands of users. LEAPS-INNOV aims to kick-start the implementation of the LEAPS Technology Roadmap and, at the same time, to foster a partnership with European industry through open innovation by offering joint technological developments and advanced research capabilities with LEAPS members for industry as collaborator, supplier and user.

Event website: <https://indico.desy.de/event/29568/>

Zoom link: <https://desy.zoom.us/j/92974199260> Passcode: 944147

Agenda

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DAY 1: 20 April 2021**9:00-10:15h Plenary Session, Day 1**

09:00h Welcome Speech, Helmut Dosch

Chair: Christian David

09:15h Introductory Statements, Patricia Postigo McLaughlin, European Commission

09:25h LEAPS-INNOV Overview, Elke Plönjes

09:45h Intellectual Property (IP): Protection and Transfer to application – what does it mean, Ilka Mahns

10:00h Q&A Session

10:15h *End of Plenary Session Day 1 & Break*

10:30h Parallel Sessions of WPs in Break out rooms (NOTE: WP4: NeXtgrating am, WP3: Superflat pm consecutively)

13:00h *End of Day 1 or Break & Option to continue in pm (up to each WP)*

18:00h *Parallel Sessions of WPs extension possible if wished by WP (18h End of Day 1)*

DAY 2: 21 April 2021**9:00 – 12:00 Plenary Session, Day 2**

Chair: Elke Plönjes

Individual LEAPS-INNOV WP presentations: 10 minutes each incl Q&A (=7'+3')

09:00 LEAPS-INNOV WP presentation: WP1

09:10 LEAPS-INNOV WP presentation: WP2

09:20h LEAPS-INNOV WP presentation: WP3

09:30h LEAPS-INNOV WP presentation: WP4

09:40h LEAPS-INNOV WP presentation: WP5

09:50h *Mini Break*

10:00h LEAPS-INNOV WP presentation: WP6

10:10h LEAPS-INNOV WP presentation: WP7

10:20h LEAPS-INNOV WP presentation: WP8

10:30h LEAPS-INNOV WP presentation: WP9

10:40h *Break*

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11:30h	LEAPS-INNOV governance, LEAPS and LEAPS-INNOV interaction, Ute Krell
11:45h	Summary of Day 2, To do's and next steps, Elke Plönjes
12:00h	<i>End of Day 2 (for all, excl. EB&GB members)</i>
12:00h	Constitutive Executive Board (EB) Meeting (Closed session, Members of EB only)
13:00h	<i>Break</i>
14:30h	Constitutive Governing Board (GB) Meeting (Closed session, Members of GB only)
15:30h	<i>End of Day 2 for GB</i>

LEAPS-INNOV kick-off Meeting Participants (as from Zoom participation)

Katharina Kucza (DESY)	David Dennetiere (SOLEIL)
Julia Hauk (DESY)	pawel wesolowski KIT
antonella balerna	Christian Morawe
Yves Watier	Elke Plönjes
Mirko Boin (HZB)	Thomas Krist
Ray Barrett	Adriana Wawrzyniak
André Hilger	Heinz Graafsma
Thomas Schmidt	Ed Mitchell
Stefan Rehbein	Rudolf Dimper (ESRF)
Fabienne Orsini (SOLEIL)	Paco Iguaz (SOLEIL)
Alison Roblin	Ed Rial
Bernd Schmitt	Lorenzo Pivetta
Nicola Tartoni (Diamond)	Martin van Breukelen
Søren Vrønning Hoffmann (ASTRID2)	David Pennicard
Søren Pape Møller	Franz Hennies
Axel Kaprolat	Tomasz Kołodziej
Michael Hagelstein	Hans-Christian Wille (DESY)
Matthias Neeb (HZB)	Steve Milward DLS
François POLACK	Darren Spruce
Kawal Sawhney	Thierry MARTIN
Silja Schmidtchen	Stefan Carlson
Bastian Klemke (HZB)	Mark Heron
Paul Bell (MAX IV)	Iakashi Iomizaki
Deike Pahl (European XFEL)	Oliver Seeck
Shepherd Ben (STFC DL AST)	Alejandro Sánchez Gueso
Jean-Claude Biasci	Cédric Bourgoïn (Soleil)
Ilka Mahns (DESY)	Óscar Matilla Barceló
Konstantin Klementiev (MAX IV)	Joan Vila-Comamala

Christian David	Michal Mlynarczyk (SOLARIS)
Johann Baader	Klaus Kiefer
Michael Kolbe PTB	Ireneusz Zadworny
Cedric COHEN (ESRF) (Cedric COHEN)	florian.doering@psi.ch
Louisa Pickworth	Doriana Orbanic (MAX IV) (Doriana Orbanic)
Olaf Schwarzkopf	Yngve Cerenius
Ralf	Rachel Freeman
Joachim Schulz	BUCAILLE
Piotr Ciochon	Austen Rose
Núria Valls Vidal	Beatrix Bugla
Jose Avila Abellan	M Osenberg
Ute Krell (DESY)	Tasneem Saleem (SOLEIL) (Tasneem Saleem)
Alexey Erko	Marie Emmanuelle Couprie
Valcarcel Orti	Atoosa Meseck
Frank Siewert	Luca Giannessi
Carles Colldelram Peroliu	Uwe Sassenberg
matteo.amati	Yves-Marie ABIVEN (SOLEIL)
Nicolas Soler (ALBA)	Uwe Flechsig
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Maurizio Vannoni	Dirk Wallacher (HZB)
Zdenek Matej (MAX IV)	Maya Kiskinova
Angela den Hollander	Joan Casas
Brigitte Gagey (SOLEIL)	Pablo Fajardo
Raffaella Geometrante	clemens
Philippe Marion	Jaroslav Wiechecki
Antonio Bonucci - European XFEL	satheesh.maheswaran@diamond.ac.uk
Rita Graceffa	Tim Wilksen
Nicolas Janvier	Michal Falowski
Andreas Grau	Simone Di Mitri
Marco Calvi (PSI)	Nicola Tartoni
Vanesa Faro Carmona	François Polack
Deike Pahl	Mohammed Ebbeni
Elizabeth Shotton	Marcos Quispe Flores
Philippe Deblay	Guillaume Blanchard
Cecilia Blasetti (Cecilia & Francesco)	Russ Woods (MAX IV)
Frank Schluenzen (DESY)	Ulrik Pedersen
Soichiro Tsujino	Babak Kalantari
Chado(SOLEIL)	Mariangela Cestelli Guidi
Sara Casalbuoni	Chado Idrissou (SOLEIL)
Robin Owen	Josep Nicolàs Roman
Fam Rack ipad pro	Ralf Hendrik Menk

